

The Changing Demographics of Hurricane At-Risk Areas in the United States (1970–2018)

Gainbi Park

Centre for Urban and Regional Development Studies, School of Geography, Politics and Sociology,
Newcastle University

January 17, 2022

Summary

This study explores the generalized patterns of demographic changes that are within hurricane-risk zones in the United States to identify which population subgroups have been at risk of hurricane hazards (storm surge and hurricane-force wind damage) over the past few decades. The longitudinal demographic datasets employed in this study were stratified by race/ethnicity and five age groups to take into account how demographic identities affect people's exposure and vulnerability to hurricane hazards. This study highlights the importance of demographic analysis to provide a more nuanced picture of population vulnerability to natural hazards.

KEYWORDS: hurricane exposure, vulnerability, at-risk population, population change

1. Introduction

Hurricanes have been the leading cause of economic casualties in the continental United States, enough to be called “billion-dollar disasters”, incurring economic losses of 16.7 billion dollars annually between 1900 and 2017. Moreover, the scientific evidence suggests that hurricanes are only expected to intensify their destructiveness and frequency in the US Gulf and Atlantic coasts owing to global climate change and rising sea surface temperatures (Emanuel, 2011; Weinkle *et al.*, 2018). Despite growing concerns over intensifying hurricane activity, population growth and economic development along the U.S. coasts have been continuously increasing, thereby placing coastal population at greater risk of multiple coastal hazards (Cutter *et al.*, 2007).

The U.S. population has experienced significant growth, diversification, and spatial redistribution in the past few decades. These changing geo-demographics (i.e., demographic profile of groups of people by where they live) have altered the social vulnerability of places across the United States (Donner and Rodríguez, 2008). In particular, hurricanes affect different populations with varying degrees of social vulnerability, primarily in coastal communities in the U.S. In this respect, this study seeks to examine how hurricane damage affects the demographic composition along America's hurricane coasts. Do hurricane weather events drive out people of higher social vulnerability status, such as minority populations, from these areas? Do the hurricane at-risk areas experience changing demographic composition over time, resulting in spatial demographic differentiation in their vulnerability?

In facing the challenge of climate change and increasing risk from natural hazards, it is important to understand how populations have been historically affected and what population groups have demonstrated the most vulnerability. As a proxy to understand differential demographic vulnerability, this study aims to unravel which demographic subgroups have been at risk of hurricane damage over the past few decades (1970–2018) by using cross-coded demographic variables stratified by race/ethnicity and five age groups. Specifically, this study seeks to examine which population segments are increasingly or decreasingly exposed to the hurricane damage over time within hurricane-prone regions – *differential demographic vulnerability* (Muttarak *et al.*, 2015). In this study, the geography of hurricane-impacted areas was spatially predefined by estimating the full extent of damage caused by storm surge and hurricane-force winds of all past hurricanes from 1950 to 2018 (Park, 2021).

2. Methods

The geographic coverage of this study is limited to the hurricane-prone coastal areas that have experienced at least one instance of storm surge inundation and wind damage between 1950 and 2018 along the Gulf of Mexico and Atlantic Coasts in the United States, excluding the Pacific Coast and the Great Lakes region (**Figure 1**). The hurricane at-risk areas were estimated using two geophysical modeling methods – a hydrodynamic Sea, Lake, and Overland Surges from Hurricanes (SLOSH) model and a meteorological hurricane surface wind reconstruction model (HURRECON) – to obtain the spatial extent and intensity of storm surge and wind damage caused by past hurricanes during the study period. The total of 190 hurricanes and tropical storms were considered in the modeling procedure. The generated surface of these hurricane-related damage by each hurricane has exhibited spatially varying geographic boundaries depending on the storm’s intensity across space and time. In order to remove any seasonal or random variability in the extent of hurricane impacts over time, the spatial layers of hurricane impacts were integrated to a singular geographic area, representing the long-term cumulative risk of hurricanes over the past several decades. The study area is the combined geographical areas of storm surge damage and F0 wind damage in the U.S. coastal region, encompassing all counties that have been affected by some category of hurricane damage (i.e., 775 counties).

Figure 1 (A) The coastal counties affected by wind damage according to the Fujita scale (F0, F1, F2, and F3); (B) the coastal census tracts inundated by 1 foot or greater storm surge flooding (census-tract level); (C) hurricane at-risk areas defined in this study: 775 counties and 21,010 census tracts (source: Park, 2021).

This study also adopts dasymetric mapping to estimate at-risk populations in developed areas

(presumably considered habitable zones) of hurricane at-risk areas using ancillary land use- and land-cover data. By combining the damage fraction of storm surge and wind damage (measured by the Fujita scale – F0, F1, F2, F3) with race- and age-specific population estimates, we can obtain the number of people that have been exposed to hurricane risks over the past five decades. For the areas affected by wind damage, this study incorporates the U.S. Intercensal County Population Data (1970–2018). For storm surge areas, census tract data from the decennial census and American Community Survey (ACS) can yield the localized impact of storm surge inundation. Both the county-level and census-tract level population data are stratified by age, race, and Hispanic origin to further examine how the extent of vulnerability varies among different segments of populations. Demographic data are stratified by four race categories (non-Hispanic White, non-Hispanic Black, non-Hispanic Others, and Hispanic) and five age groups as follows: age group 1 (0–4 years), age group 2 (5–19 years), age group 3 (20–34 years), age group 4 (35–64 years), and age group 5 (65 years and older). To grasp the age-race specific population exposure representativeness to hurricane-related damage, both the percentage of populations residing in varying degrees of hurricane damage zones and their share of the population within the study area over time are calculated.

3. Results

Figure 2 presents the hurricane-prone areas at the county level as illustrated in Figure 1c. It is evident that the Black population has hovered around 15 to 18 percent since 1970 in the hurricane-prone counties, demonstrating that there is a higher concentration of Blacks within the path of cumulative hurricane risk. In terms of the Hispanic population, there is a slightly higher population distribution within the hurricane-prone counties, showing a 1-2 percent greater population gap in comparison with the outside area. The age-distribution within the hurricane-prone area also appears to skew more towards the older generation with a higher concentration of age groups 3, 4, and 5 than the counties outside of the hurricane-prone area. The non-Hispanic Others show similar growth patterns both inside and outside, however, there is a slightly higher concentration of this group outside of the hurricane-prone counties. The non-Hispanic White group has been dominant throughout the study period. Remarkably, however, this group has been declining, consistent with the national trend, with an age composition more heavily weighted towards the middle-aged and older generation.

Figure 2 Population composition within the hurricane-prone counties (n=775)

This study further dissects the demographic trends within the specific hurricane damage categories through two lens, focusing on the cross-coded demographic variables, race and age. This distribution varies among different damage categories.

4. Conclusion

This research integrates geographic and demographic perspectives to enrich the approach to vulnerability assessment of natural hazards adopting a population-environment research paradigm (Crawford, Bradley, & Marcucci, 2013). This is a comprehensive assessment on hurricane-specific population vulnerability in the U.S. Atlantic and Gulf Coasts over the past decades. Despite its descriptive and exploratory nature, this study offers some insights into population vulnerability to hurricane-related damage urging policy makers to adopt demographic perspectives to make informed decisions for disaster risk management. Knowing what population groups are at greater risk of hurricanes is important to disclose differential vulnerability among population segments. The findings of this research provide a comprehensive understanding of spatial and temporal patterns of demographic change in US coastal regions and can assist policymakers in supporting disaster emergency planning and evacuation strategies in a meaningful manner.

5. Acknowledgements

Portions of this extended abstract is based on a paper published in *ISPRS International Journal of Geo-Information* (Park, 2021) and a manuscript in review.

References

- Crawford, T.W., Bradley, D.E. and Marcucci, D.J., 2013. Impacts of in-migration and coastal amenities on housing growth in coastal North Carolina, United States. *Population, Space and Place*, 19(3), pp.223-238.
- Cutter, S.L., Johnson, L.A., Finch, C. and Berry, M., 2007. The US hurricane coasts: increasingly vulnerable?. *Environment: Science and Policy for Sustainable Development*, 49(7), pp.8-21.
- Donner, W. and Rodríguez, H., 2008. Population composition, migration and inequality: The influence of demographic changes on disaster risk and vulnerability. *Social forces*, 87(2), pp.1089-1114.
- Emanuel, K., 2011. Global warming effects on US hurricane damage. *Weather, Climate, and Society*, 3(4), pp.261-268.
- Muttarak, R., Lutz, W. and Jiang, L., 2015. What can demographers contribute to the study of vulnerability?. *Vienna Yearbook of Population Research*, 13, pp.1-13.
- Park, G., 2021. A Comprehensive Analysis of Hurricane Damage across the US Gulf and Atlantic Coasts Using Geospatial Big Data. *ISPRS International Journal of Geo-Information*, 10(11), p.781.
- Weinkle, J., Landsea, C., Collins, D., Musulin, R., Crompton, R.P., Klotzbach, P.J. and Pielke, R., 2018. Normalized hurricane damage in the continental United States 1900–2017. *Nature Sustainability*, 1(12), pp.808-813.

Biographies

Gainbi Park is a research fellow at the Centre for Urban and Regional Development Studies (CURDS) within the School of Geography, Politics and Sociology at Newcastle University. She received her PhD at the University of Wisconsin-Milwaukee in 2021. Her research leans toward GIScience with a focus on the social vulnerability to natural hazards and geodemographics.